

Role of electrolytes composition, ionic crossover and CO₂ availability in bioelectrochemical methanation

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ABSTRACT

Bioelectrochemical methanation (BEM) is a promising carbon capture and utilization (CCU) technology that converts CO₂ and renewable electricity into synthetic methane under mild operating conditions. However, the performance and stability of BEM stacks are strongly influenced by electrolyte composition, ionic crossover and carbon availability, factors that remain poorly understood beyond single-cell systems. In this work, a three-cell BEM stack was operated under galvanostatic control for 83 days to systematically investigate the combined effects of electrolyte composition, applied current density and dissolved CO₂ concentration on methane production, purity and electrochemical efficiency. The stack was operated at 6 and 12 A m⁻², while dissolved CO₂ in the catholyte was progressively reduced from near saturation to < 0.22 g L⁻¹. Results show that excessive ionic crossover led to salt accumulation and partial inhibition of methanogenesis, which was mitigated by electrolyte replacement that restored microbial activity and stabilized conductivity below inhibitory thresholds. Lower dissolved CO₂ concentrations significantly improved CH₄ purity (up to 88%) while sustaining high production rates (1.1 ± 0.3 L-CH₄ L_{cathode}⁻¹ d⁻¹) and cathodic Coulombic efficiencies up to 99%. Ion balance analysis revealed that charge transport was dominated by cations and phosphate species rather than protons, contributing to increased ohmic and pH-related losses. Overall, this study demonstrates that controlling dissolved CO₂ availability and managing ionic crossover in BEM stacks are critical levers for optimizing their performances. These findings provide practical guidance for electrolyte design and CO₂ delivery strategies in BEM systems, supporting the development of scalable bioelectrochemical routes for CO₂ utilization.

1. Introduction

Bioelectrochemical methanation (BEM), also referred to as electro-methanogenesis, is a promising carbon capture and utilization (CCU) technology for power-to-gas (P2G) applications, enabling the conversion of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and renewable electricity into synthetic methane (CH₄) [1]. By coupling electrochemical hydrogen generation with microbial catalysis, BEM offers a flexible route for carbon recycling, grid balancing and long-term energy storage. Compared with conventional thermochemical methanation, bioelectrochemical systems operate at mild temperature and pressure conditions, tolerate gas impurities, and can be directly coupled to intermittent renewable energy sources, making them attractive for decentralized and circular energy

systems. BEM was increasingly compared also to biological methanation [2], but differs in that BEM supplies directly the electrons to the process via the cathode, eliminating the need for external hydrogen infrastructure. This in situ electron delivery is fundamental to the operation of BEM and defines the mechanisms by which CH₄ is produced. Specifically, CO₂ reduction to CH₄ at the cathode may proceed either through direct extracellular electron uptake by methanogens or, more commonly, through an indirect pathway in which electrochemically generated H₂ is consumed by hydrogenotrophic methanogens [3,4]. Although the relative contribution of these pathways remains debated and may depend on cathode material, reactor configuration, and microbial community composition, several studies indicate that H₂-mediated methanogenesis is often the dominant mechanism under practical

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operating conditions [5–7]. Early works by Cheng et al. [3] and Villano et al. [4] established the theoretical framework for both pathways, and subsequent studies using isotopic labelling and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy provided further mechanistic evidence in single-cell configuration [5,8], though a unified mechanistic picture under stack-level conditions remains absent from the literature.

A typical BEM cell consists of an anodic and a cathodic chamber separated by an ion-exchange membrane and connected through an external electrical circuit [6]. At the anode, water oxidation supplies electrons and protons, while at the cathode, microorganisms catalyse the conversion of CO₂ to CH₄ using reducing equivalents supplied electrochemically [5]. In many cell designs, a cation exchange membrane (CEM) is used to maintain electroneutrality by facilitating proton and cation transport while limiting anion migration [9]. Previous studies showed that this configuration is effective for laboratory-scale operation; however, membrane-based separation also introduces transport limitations, pH imbalances, and ion crossover phenomena that can progressively affect reactor stability, particularly during long-term operation [9–11]. Sleutels et al. [10] demonstrated that cation transport through CEMs, rather than proton transport alone, is responsible for the majority of charge transfer in microbial electrochemical systems, leading to pH imbalances that are difficult to control over time. These issues are expected to become more pronounced as systems move from single-cell configurations toward stacked architectures, where ionic transport resistance and cumulative electrolyte imbalances may be amplified.

Among the factors governing BEM performance, electrolyte composition plays a particularly important role because it influences ionic conductivity, membrane transport, pH stability and microbial activity. On the anodic side, acidic electrolytes are frequently used to facilitate proton transport and reduce internal resistance of the cell. However, prolonged operation at low pH and under strongly oxidizing conditions may accelerate electrode corrosion, increase oxygen evolution overpotentials and affect the durability of cell components [12]. On the cathodic side, conductive electrolytes are required to minimize ohmic losses and sustain efficient electron transfer, yet increasing ionic strength may also intensify non-selective ion crossover across the membrane.

As reported in previous studies, the resulting accumulation of salts in the catholyte can increase osmotic stress and inhibit methanogenic activity, especially in non-adapted communities [13,14]. To address this, halotolerant methanogens have been investigated as a strategy to maintain CH₄ production under elevated salinity conditions [15,16]. A recent study by Lang et al. [16] demonstrated that optimizing electrolyte conductivity in a BEM system resulted in a three-fold increase in current density while maintaining stable microbial operation over multiple hundred hours, a result that underscores the importance of electrolyte design but was achieved in a single-cell configuration, leaving open the question of how these effects scale in stacked systems. These findings highlight a central trade-off in BEM operation: electrolyte conditions that are favourable for electrochemical performance are not always compatible with long-term microbial stability.

In parallel with ionic transport constraints, CO₂ availability in the cathode compartment represents a key yet often overlooked factor in BEM operation. Many laboratory studies have relied on bicarbonate-buffered catholytes as a readily available inorganic carbon source and as a means to stabilize pH [6,17]. While useful for fundamental investigations, this approach does not fully reflect industrial CCU scenarios, in which gaseous CO₂ streams are more likely to be supplied directly. Under such conditions, gas-liquid mass transfer becomes a major bottleneck because CO₂ has relatively low solubility in water, approximately 1.1 g-CO₂ L⁻¹ at 35 °C and atmospheric pressure [18]. Several electrochemical and bioelectrochemical studies have shown that insufficient dissolved CO₂ can limit conversion rates, alter local pH and reduce overall carbon utilization [14,17,19]. While gas-liquid CO₂ transfer limitations were characterized in bioelectrochemical systems

[17], their interaction with microbial kinetics and membrane transport in long-term BEM operation has received comparatively little attention, particularly under conditions of progressively depleted dissolved CO₂. In addition, dissolved CO₂ may diffuse through the membrane as an uncharged species, contributing to carbon losses, anodic gas contamination and lower methane purity [19].

Although these effects were individually recognized, they were often investigated separately, and their combined interaction with electrolyte composition, ion transport and current density remains insufficiently resolved.

In this work, we address these knowledge gaps by investigating the operational factors that influence the performance of a lab-scale BEM stack. The study pursues three main objectives: (i) to optimize anolyte and catholyte compositions for a balance between ionic conductivity and microbial compatibility, (ii) to evaluate the effects of operational current density and (iii) to assess how different dissolved CO₂ regimes affect methane production rate, gas purity and Coulombic efficiency. To this end, the stack was operated under galvanostatic control for 83 days, combining electrochemical characterization with detailed analysis of ion crossover, gas composition and dissolved CO₂ dynamics. In parallel, microbial community structure and methanogenic activity were monitored through 16S rRNA sequencing and functional gene quantification.

This study provides for the first time a deeper understanding of how ion transport, carbon availability and microbial activity collectively shape BEM stack performance. The results contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of how electrolyte management and CO₂ delivery strategies can be leveraged to enhance methane production efficiency, purity and long-term stability, thereby supporting the development of scalable bioelectrochemical routes for CO₂ utilization.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Laboratory setup

Three double-chambered, flat plate BEM cells (named BEM 1, 2 and 3) were constructed, each one with a transversal section of 100 cm² and a thickness of 2 cm, corresponding to a chamber volume of 200 mL (Fig. 1). The anode consisted of a 9 cm² titanium mesh coated with 12 g m⁻² of iridium oxide-based mixed metal oxide (IrO₂ MMO; Magneto, The Netherlands), soldered to a 6 mm diameter titanium rod serving as the current collector. The cathode chamber was packed with ~10 g of stainless-steel wool (RAKSO Stainless Steel Wool Medium INOX 434, RAKSO, Germany) and a 6 mm diameter titanium rod (GoodFellow, UK) served as current collector. An Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode (+208 mV vs SHE, Xi'an Yima Opto-electrical Technology, China) was inserted into each chamber. A CEM (100 cm², CMHPP RALEX, MemBrain s.r.o., Czech Republic) was used as separator between anode and cathode chambers. The three cells were powered by individual power sources (TENMA 72–2715, Farnell, Spain). For each one, the negative terminal was connected to the cathode and the positive terminal to the anode (two-electrode configuration).

Cell voltage and individual electrode potentials were measured manually with a multimeter (30XR-A Digital Multimeter, Amprobe). The overpotential of each cell was also manually measured, as the potential difference existing between the reference electrode placed in the anode chamber and the one placed in the cathode chamber.

The anolyte of each BEM cell was continuously recirculated at a rate of 200 mL min⁻¹ to a common recirculation bottle of 2 L, where the produced oxygen was separated from the liquid anolyte. The anolyte circuit was maintained at an overpressure of 180–200 mbar by a non-return valve located in the single, oxygen outflow line, which opened at that pressure range. The pressure of the circuit was monitored with a digital pressure indicator (PS42, E-MC, China). Gas production was quantified using a flowmeter (BlueVCount, BlueSens, Germany) and logged onto a computer via BlueVis software (BlueSens, Germany).

The catholyte of the 3 BEM cells was recirculated at a rate of

Fig. 1. Laboratory system schematics (only one BEM cell of the stack is shown for simplicity).

200 mL min⁻¹ to a shared recirculation bottle of 3 L, where the produced biogas was separated from the liquid phase. A dissolved CO₂ sensor (InPro5000i, Mettler Toledo, Spain) was integrated into the catholyte recirculation line, to measure the CO₂ concentration in the liquid phase (CO₂(aq)). The data was logged by the corresponding transmitter unit (M400, Mettler Toledo, Spain). The catholyte temperature was regulated using a thermostat (CC-215B, Huber, Germany) connected to a plate-exchange heater (Hrale B3-12-30, Ningbo Hrale Plate Heat Exchanger Co., Ltd., China). The thermostat was connected to a temperature probe inserted in the catholyte recirculation line circuit, which adjusted the heating water temperature to maintain the setpoint of 35°C.

The catholyte circuit, like the anolyte one, was kept at an overpressure of 180–200 mbar via a non-return valve installed in the single, combined CH₄ outflow line, with pressure monitored by a digital probe. The produced gas was quantified by a flowmeter (BlueVCount, BlueSens, Germany) and logged using BlueVis software (BlueSens, Germany). CH₄ and CO₂ concentrations in the gas outflow were measured with two BCP infrared sensors (BlueSens, Germany), with data recorded using the BlueVis software.

2.2. Electrolyte compositions

Two mineral media were used as catholyte: Electrolyte-A and Electrolyte-B, simulating nutrient-rich wastewater effluents with low carbon content (Table 1). The electrolytes were replenished whenever the volume in the recirculation bottles decreased to less than one-third of its initial level, due to periodic liquid sampling.

A methanogenic-enriched culture was obtained from the sludge of an anaerobic digester at a local wastewater treatment plant in Terrassa, Spain, as described in a previous study [20]. For biocathode inoculation, the biomass was allowed to settle, and 300 mL of the sediment were injected into the cathode chambers under strictly anaerobic conditions.

During the first 44 days of experimentation, Electrolyte-A served as

Table 1

Composition of the two catholyte mineral media utilized in the present work. The formulation of the trace element solution and Wolfe Vitamin solution are reported in Supplementary information (Table S1).

Component	Electrolyte-A	Electrolyte-B	Units
Na ₂ HPO ₄ × 12 H ₂ O	11.7	0.35	g L ⁻¹
KH ₂ PO ₄	2.54	0.23	g L ⁻¹
NH ₄ Cl	0.53	0.50	g L ⁻¹
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.1	0.1	g L ⁻¹
KCl	0.052	-	g L ⁻¹
CaCl ₂ × 2 H ₂ O	0.01	0.25	g L ⁻¹
MgCl ₂ × 6 H ₂ O	0.72	0.41	g L ⁻¹
NaHCO ₃	-	0.85	g L ⁻¹
Cysteine Hydrochloride	-	0.3	g L ⁻¹
Trace elements solution	1	1	mL L ⁻¹
Wolfe Vitamin Solution (1000×)	1	1	mL L ⁻¹
pH	7.5	7.7	-
Conductivity	15.1	4.0	mS cm ⁻¹

the catholyte. To mitigate the accumulation of salts in the catholyte, exacerbated by cation transport from the anode compartment through the CEM, 30% of the catholyte volume was replaced once with Electrolyte-B. This partial substitution also aimed to resemble the lower conductivity (4 mS cm⁻¹, Table 1) typically found in real exhausted wastewater effluents.

Initially, the adopted anolyte was a 0.1 M potassium phosphate monobasic solution (PPMS), with the pH adjusted with NaOH to ~7.4 (P3619-1GA, Sigma-Aldrich). The PPMS had an initial conductivity of 14.1 mS cm⁻¹. On day 63, the PPMS anolyte was completely replaced with Electrolyte-B to prevent ion diffusion through the CEM, which could arise from the high ion concentration gradient between the PPMS anolyte and Electrolyte-B.

2.3. Experimental design

The BEM stack was hydraulically operated in batch for 83 days (Table 2), through which the combined effect of dissolved CO₂ concentration in the catholyte and the applied current density was investigated. The cells were controlled in galvanostatic mode, initially at 6 A m⁻² (starting value based on [11]). Unless otherwise specified, current densities are normalized to the cathode's planar surface area (100 cm²). From a scale-up perspective, galvanostatic control is advantageous as it enables fine control over electron flow to match the CO₂ supply rate, thereby optimizing CH₄ production. After 14 days of operation, the current density was increased to 12 A m⁻², as no excess H₂ was detected in the catholyte gas outlet, indicating that the available reducing equivalents were fully consumed by the electromethanogenic process.

The cathode chamber of the BEM stack was batch-fed with pure CO₂ gas (99.995%, Carburas Metalicos, Spain), regularly sparged into the catholyte trough a porous stone diffuser situated in the recirculation bottle. The injection rate (20 mL min⁻¹) was regulated by a mass flow controller (MFC D-6411 Bronkhorst, Iberfluid, Spain).

The progressive reduction of dissolved CO₂ concentration throughout the different operational phases was implemented to minimize carbon losses to the anodic compartment and to enhance the purity of the oxygen produced. Under operating conditions at pH values between 7 and 8, dissolved inorganic carbon is predominantly present as bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻). Although the CEM restricts the transport of anionic species and thus limits carbonate migration, carbon crossover can still occur via diffusion of dissolved CO₂ (CO₂ (aq)), a non-ionized species capable of permeating the membrane. During the inoculation and start-up phases (first 21 days), CO₂ gas was injected whenever its dissolved concentration in the catholyte dropped below 0.55 g L⁻¹ (50% of its solubility limit) and stopped when it exceeded 1.1 g L⁻¹ (100%), to ensure continuous substrate availability. From day 21–63 (until the anolyte exchange), CO₂ injection ceased once its dissolved concentration surpassed 0.88 g L⁻¹. Between days 64 and 76, dissolved CO₂ level was regulated to stay within 0.66–0.22 g L⁻¹. In the final operational phase (days 76–83), the dissolved CO₂ concentration was maintained between 0.22 and 0.055 g L⁻¹ (Table 2). It should be noted that this regulation was performed manually based on the CO₂ dissolved sensor readings, and therefore the control of CO₂ concentration was not perfectly accurate.

2.4. Electrochemical characterization

Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV) was performed on the cathodes of the three cells before their inoculation (abiotic condition) and after 28 days of operation, to assess the development and electrochemical activity of the electromethanogenic biofilm. Measurements were conducted at a scan rate of 1 mV s⁻¹, with the cathodic potential ranging from -0.50 V to -1.20 V vs Ag/AgCl. The experiments were carried out using a portable potentiostat (SP-150, BioLogic, France) in a three-electrode configuration, where the cathode served as the working electrode, the anode as the counter electrode, and an Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl)

Table 2
Experimental timeline.

Phase	Time (days)	Current density (A m ⁻²)	Anolyte	Catholyte	Dissolved CO ₂ range	
					(%)	(g-CO ₂ L ⁻¹)
Start-up	0–14	6	PPMS	Electrolyte-A	100–50	1.1–0.55
	15–21	12	PPMS	Electrolyte-A	100–50	1.1–0.55
Operation	21–44	12	PPMS	Electrolyte-A	80–50	0.88–0.55
	44	Catholyte exchange				
	45–63	12	PPMS	Electrolyte-B	80–50	0.88–0.55
	63	Anolyte exchange				
	64–76	12	Electrolyte-B	Electrolyte-B	60–20	0.66–0.22
	76–83	12	Electrolyte-B	Electrolyte-B	20–5	0.22–0.055

electrode, placed in the cathode chamber, as reference. During the measurements, no external CO₂ was supplied during the tests.

Theoretical calculations for overpotentials of the BEM stack were performed following protocols available in [10,21]. This analysis allowed to identify overpotentials in the BEM stack, their distribution among the different electrochemical processes, and their evolution under the different operating conditions. Specifically, overpotentials due to pH gradients across the membrane (η_{pH}), and electrolyte resistance (η_{ionic}) were calculated. Additional contributions that could not be individually quantified (e.g., anodic and cathodic activation losses, membrane resistance, and other transport-related resistances) were grouped under the name $\eta_{unknown}$ in Eq. (1).

$$\sum \eta (V) = \eta_{pH} + \eta_{ionic} + \eta_{unknown} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

During operation, a pH gradient developed over the membrane, resulting overpotential. This contribution was calculated according to Eq. (2).

$$\eta_{pH}(V) = \frac{RT}{F} \ln(10^{(pH_{cat} - pH_{an})}) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where F is the Faraday's constant (96485 C mol⁻¹), R is the universal gas constant (8.314 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) and T is the temperature (K).

The overpotential associated to the electrolyte resistance was determined using Eq. (3).

$$\eta_{ionic}(V) = I_{ions} \left(\frac{1}{2} R_{an} + \frac{1}{2} R_{cat} \right) = I_{ions} \left(\frac{d_{an}}{2A\sigma_{an}} + \frac{d_{cat}}{2A\sigma_{cat}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Here, I_{ions} represent the amount of charges migrated through the membrane (the value is the same of the registered electric current of the BEM stack (C·s = A)), R is the resistance of the liquid phase, calculated from the electrode-membrane distance (d, cm), the effective membrane area (A, cm²), and the conductivity of the electrolyte (σ , S cm⁻¹).

Finally, the cell overpotential ($\sum \eta$) was also calculated by comparing the experimental cell voltage (V Cell_{experimental}) with the cell voltage reconstructed from the individual electrode potentials (V Cell_{measured}) as described in Eq. (4). By combining Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) with the cell overpotential obtained from Eq. (4), the remaining unquantified contribution ($\eta_{unknown}$) was determined by difference.

$$\sum \eta (V) = V_{Cell_{experimental}} - V_{Cell_{measured}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Where V Cell_{experimental} is the potential difference between the anode and the cathode measured during operation, and V Cell_{measured} is the reconstructed cell voltage calculated from the individual electrode potentials according to Eq. (5):

$$V_{Cell_{measured}} (V) = E_{cathode_m} - E_{anode_m} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

in which E_{cathode_m} and E_{anode_m} are the cathode and anode potentials, respectively, measured vs their corresponding reference electrode placed in each chamber.

2.5. Liquid and gas analysis

Liquid samples (~20 mL) were periodically collected and analysed for pH and conductivity using a HQ40 multimeter (Hach Lange, Spain). Chloride (Cl⁻), sulphate (SO₄²⁻) and phosphate (PO₄³⁻) anions were quantified for each sample using an ionic chromatograph (ICS-3000, Dionex, Spain) while sodium (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺), calcium (Ca²⁺), and magnesium (Mg²⁺) cations were quantified by the means of Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (AGILENT 8900 ICP-QQQ, Agilent Technologies, Spain).

Volatile Fatty Acids (VFAs), including acetate, propionate, butyrate, valerate and hexanoate, presents in the liquid phase were subjected to analysis using an ionic chromatograph (ICS-3000 Conductivity Detector, Dionex).

The optical density of catholyte samples was measured at a wavelength of 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) with a Hach DR 3900 spectrophotometer, to estimate the growth of the planktonic microbial community in the electrolyte.

Ex situ gas samples were also collected, both from anolyte and catholyte circuits. Their volumetric composition (in terms of CH₄, CO₂, H₂, O₂, N₂, CO and H₂S) was determined by using a gas chromatograph (490 Micro GC Natural Gas Analyzer, Agilent, Spain), as reported in Ref. [22].

2.6. Other calculations

For the following calculations, the BEM stack was considered as a single unit system. The specific CH₄ production rate (r_{CH_4}) of the stack was calculated (in L L⁻¹ d⁻¹, referred to cathode chamber volume). Analogously, the specific oxygen production rate (r_{O_2}) at the anode was calculated using the recorded O₂ volume and the total anode surface area (27 cm²). Cathode Coulombic Efficiency (CE_{cat}) was calculated as the percentage of electrons effectively used to reduce CO₂ into CH₄ relative to the total electrons supplied. The results are presented as average daily CE_{cat}.

Energy consumption (E_{con}) was calculated by dividing the power input (kWh) of the BEM stack by the volume of produced CH₄ in normal conditions (Eq. (6)).

$$E_{con} (\text{kWh Nm}^{-3}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (I_{cell,i} \cdot E_{cell,i}) * 24 \text{ h}}{V_{CH_4}} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

The individual ionic contribution (i_{ion}) of selected ions to the total charge transport in the BEM unit was calculated by Eq. (7), derived from [23]. The considered ions were Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, and PO₄³⁻ as anions, Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺ as cations.

$$i_{ion} (\text{C s}^{-1} \text{ m}_{membrane}^{-2}) = \frac{Z \cdot F \cdot V \cdot \Delta[C_{ion}]}{A \cdot t} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

Where Z is the ionic charge (dimensionless), V is the volume of the compartment where ion concentration is measured (L), A is the total membrane area (m²) and Δ[C_{ion}] is the difference in concentration of ions (mol L⁻¹).

2.7. Microbiological analysis

12 liquid samples from the catholyte's bulk were collected during BEM start-up and operation. Over the 83 days of operation, two distinct phases were identified for microbial analysis: Phase 1, corresponding to the period before the catholyte exchange, and Phase 2, corresponding to the period after the exchange. All samples were collected from the bulk catholyte, ensuring a non-invasive approach that avoided disturbing the microbial community established in the cathodic biofilm. Sampling was done under sterile conditions and samples were transferred into DNase-free Eppendorf tubes and stored at -20°C. DNA was extracted using a

commercially available extraction kit (ZymoBIOMICS™ DNA Miniprep Kit, Zymo Research, Irvine, CA, USA), according to the manufacturer's protocol. The DNA concentration was measured using a Qubit Fluorometer and the dsDNA HS Assay kit (both Invitrogen, USA). The expression of methanogenic genes *mcrA* (methyl-coenzyme M reductase alpha subunit) and *hdrA* (heterodisulphide reductase subunit A), critical for methanogenesis, was quantified using Quantitative PCR (QuantStudio 5, ThermoFisher, USA.), while the full-length 16S rRNA gene (~1.5 kb) were sequenced to assess microbial community composition.

Library preparation was carried out following the DNA 16S Barcoding Kit 24 V14 protocol (SQK-16S114.24, Oxford Nanopore Technologies, UK), except for the PCR amplification step, in which the LongAmp Hot Start Taq 2X Master Mix (New England Biolabs) was replaced with repliQa HiFi ToughMix (Quantabio) to optimize and expedite the process. The PCR program was conducted under the following conditions: initial denaturation at 98°C for 3 s; 35 cycles of denaturation at 98°C for 10 s, annealing at 55°C for 5 s, and extension at 68°C for 5 s; followed by a final extension at 68°C for 1 min. The 16S rRNA gene amplicons were sequenced using a MinION device and an R10.4.1 flow cell. The raw sequencing (FAST5) reads were processed with dorado 1.0.1 basecaller in SUP mode. 16S rRNA workflow from EPI2ME (Nextflow) was used for taxonomic classification and data abundance table generation. NCBI 16S + 18S rRNA database was used for taxonomic assignment. Data visualization and statistical analyses were performed in R Studio using phyloseq [24] and microeco [25] packages.

Methanogenic genes specific primers and plasmids were designed using references from literature [8,26], the NCBI BLAST database, and the GeneArt gene synthesis services (Thermo Fisher, Life Sciences) (Supplementary information, Table S2). The *hdrA* gene encodes a key enzyme essential for anaerobic respiration in methane-producing archaea [8]. The *mcrA* gene encodes the α subunit of methyl coenzyme M reductase, the enzyme responsible for catalysing the final step in methanogenesis [26]. The qPCR reactions were run in volumes of 10 μL, containing 5 μL of Power Track SyBR Green Master Mix (Applied biosystems), 0.5 μL of each primer (10 μM), and 4 μL of plasmid or DNA template. PCR amplification was carried out with the following protocol: 5 min at 95°C and 40 cycles of 10 s at 95°C, 1 min at 55°C, and 10 s at 72°C. Standard curve equations (Eq. (10) and Eq. (11)) for copies quantifications are detailed for each primer on Table S3 (Supplementary information). qPCR data analysis involved calculating Ct values and gene copy numbers in Excel, with further statistical analysis and data visualization conducted in R Studio.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Optimization of electrolytes

The biocathodes of the three BEM cells were inoculated with an enriched methanogenic culture. For their start-up, the cells were operated under galvanostatic control at a current density of 6 A m⁻². The catholyte conductivity increased, rising from 9.5 mS cm⁻¹ to 22 mS cm⁻¹ by day 44 (Fig. 2A), likely due to cation crossover from the anode to the cathode compartment through the CEM. This rise in conductivity approaches or exceeds the salinity tolerance limit for *Methanobacteria* (around 18 mS cm⁻¹ [27]), potentially causing partial inhibition of methanogenesis. To mitigate potential microbial inhibition caused by high salt concentrations, 30% of Electrolyte-A was replaced on day 44 with Electrolyte -B, reducing catholyte conductivity to 16.9 mS cm⁻¹ and stabilising it below 19 mS cm⁻¹, which allowed microbial activity to recover.

Until day 44 of operation, catholyte pH ranged between 6.7 and 7.7, with a punctual basification to 8.9 on day 35 (Fig. 2B). On day 38 of operation, the inoculation process previously described was repeated, due to loss of methanogenic activity in the BEM stack. The pH remained within the accepted operation range (6.75–9.2) for *Methanobacteria* [27]

Fig. 2. (A) Evolution of electrolytes conductivity and OD₆₀₀ in catholyte. (B) Evolution of electrolytes pH. Key events, including catholyte exchange (day 44) and anolyte exchange (day 63), are marked with dashed purple vertical lines.

due to the solubilization of CO₂ gas into the electrolyte. Following the catholyte exchange, the cathode pH gradually increased to around 8, due to the lower buffer capacity of the medium. The pH then remained stable at this level for the rest of the experiment.

The initial anolyte (PPMS 0.1 M) started with a neutral pH but its buffer capacity broke within two days, dropping to pH 2, where it remained stable for the rest of the experiment (Fig. 2B). This acidification was primarily due to the water oxidation reaction taking place at the anode, generating and accumulating protons (H⁺). When the anolyte composition was adjusted to be the same of Electrolyte-B, its pH temporarily increased to approximately 7. This increase was short-lived, and the pH soon returned to 2 due to the continued formation of H⁺ from the ongoing oxidation reaction. Once a dynamic balance between H⁺ generation and their transport through the CEM was reached, further H⁺ production did not affect further the anolyte pH. During the first 10 days, anolyte conductivity decreased from 15.6 to 10.9 mS cm⁻¹ (Fig. 2B), in contrast to the increasing conductivity observed in the catholyte, due to the progressing ion crossover between compartments. After day 10, the anolyte conductivity stabilized around 10 mS cm⁻¹. However, it dropped down to 7–8 mS cm⁻¹ after anolyte exchange on day 63. These shifts underline the importance of electrolyte management to maintain optimal ionic conditions and prevent excessive overpotentials.

Immediately after inoculation, OD₆₀₀ dropped from 0.3 to 0.1 (Fig. 2), likely as biomass adhered to the electrode surface to initiate

biofilm formation. OD₆₀₀ gradually increased to 0.2 indicating planktonic microorganisms' growth within the catholyte bulk (Fig. 2). After catholyte replacement (day 44), the OD₆₀₀ gradually rose from 0.2 to almost 0.7, at the end of the experiment, due to the successful development of a mixed microbial community.

The LSV measurements allowed evaluation of the catalytic properties of the cathode material in abiotic conditions as well as the enhancement in catalysis of the HER kinetics due to the biofilm growth (Supplementary information, Fig. S1). Analysing the respective LSV curves with the inoculated biocathode, revealed similar trends across all three BEM cells. At approximately -0.80 V vs Ag/AgCl, a small electroreductive current density was observed, which increased gradually to a maximum of 70 A m⁻² (83 A g⁻¹) at -1.20 V vs Ag/AgCl. The biocathode formation led to a 1.8x enhancement in current density relative to the abiotic cathode (25 A m⁻² at -1.20 V vs Ag/AgCl). However, the absolute current values suggest that further electrode optimization may be needed to maximize methane production at higher applied current densities.

3.2. Gas composition dynamics and electrochemical characterization of BEM stack

Fig. 3 show the volumetric composition of the gases produced within the cathode (A) and anode (B) chambers of the BEM stack, respectively, over the 83-day operational period. Gas composition was determined

Fig. 3. Cathodic (A) and anodic (B) gas composition (CH₄, CO₂, H₂, and O₂) across 82 days of operation. The volumetric percentage of each gas component is shown for specific time points. No CO or H₂S were detected in either case and O₂ and N₂ from air were excluded from the gas chromatography results as considered due to intrusion during sampling. (C) Evolution of cells voltage (V Cell_{experimental}), electrode potentials (E_{anode,m} and E_{cathode,m}), cells overpotential and current density. For each variable, the solid line shows the average value and the shaded area represents the corresponding standard deviation, considering the three cells of the BEM stack. Key events, including catholyte exchange (day 44) and anolyte exchange (day 63), are marked with dashed purple vertical lines.

from discrete measurements using micro-gas chromatography. The electrochemical performance of each BEM cell was monitored through offline discrete measurements of each individual electrode potentials, cell voltage and cell overpotential (Fig. 3C).

At the cathode side, the gas phase composition on day 2 was dominated by CO₂ (85%) and H₂ (13%), with only $\approx 2\%$ CH₄, reflecting the typical slow growth kinetics of methanogenic microorganisms, such as *Methanobacteria* (around 0.18 h⁻¹ under mesophilic conditions [27]). During this initial period, the BEM stack operated galvanostatically at 6 A m⁻², with stable cathode potentials near -1 V vs Ag/AgCl (Fig. 3C), indicating sustained HER activity that provided reducing equivalents for hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis.

From day 2 onwards, CH₄ progressively increased while CO₂ decreased in the cathode gas mixture, indicating successful establishment of the electromethanogenic process. By day 14, CH₄ became the dominant gas, coinciding with stable cell voltages (~ 2.6 V) and low measured overpotentials (0.13 ± 0.07 V), suggesting balanced ion transport and efficient electrochemical operation. From day 14 onward, r_{CH_4} ranged between 0.9 and 1.1 L-CH₄ L_{cathode}⁻¹ day⁻¹, with CH₄ purity exceeding 96% (days 72 and 82), demonstrating sustained biological and electrochemical stability. On day 80, a notable accumulation of H₂ and complete absence of CO₂ were observed in the cathodic gas phase. Given the overall system evolution and stable electrochemical performance, this event is most likely attributed to a sampling-time effect rather than an alteration in the BEM system performance.

At the anode side (Fig. 3B), O₂ was the predominant gas, reaching approximately 92% purity with a r_{O_2} of 3.4 L-O₂ L_{anode}⁻¹ day⁻¹ from day 21 onward. The main impurity in the O₂-rich gas was CO₂, which likely crossed from the cathode chamber. During start-up, the catholyte pH ranged between 6.5 and 7 (Fig. 2B), conditions which dissolved inorganic carbon is mainly present as HCO₃⁻, with a smaller fraction of CO₂(aq). This facilitated CO₂ transport across the membrane, contributing to anodic gas contamination. Minor amounts of CH₄ (0.0–7.7%) and H₂ (0.0–1.7%) were also detected at the anode, confirming minor gas crossover through the membrane (Fig. 3B).

Given the stable performance observed at 6 A m⁻², the current density was increased to 12 A m⁻² to evaluate the BEM stack's response under higher electron flux and to enhance CH₄ production. The resulting rise in cell voltage (3.3–3.7 V, Fig. 3C) was primarily attributed to increased electrolyte resistance which nearly doubled their contribution to the total overpotential (Supplementary information, Fig. S2), while cathode potentials remained largely unaffected. This suggests that the system was no longer primarily limited by electron availability at the cathode, and that ion transport likely became a dominant limiting factor. However, the presence of unresolved losses prevents a definitive attribution, as additional contributions from electrode kinetics, membrane resistance, and mass transport limitations may also be involved. Therefore, the relative importance of the different overpotential contributions should be interpreted with caution. Overall, these results demonstrate that the electromethanogenic process can sustain a current density of 12 A m⁻² without compromising biological activity or gas purity.

A rapid decrease in anolyte pH to approximately 2 was observed within the first two days of operation (Fig. 2B), generating a substantial pH gradient between anode and cathode chambers. This pH split increased the pH-related overpotential (Supplementary information, η_{pH} , Fig. S2), making it a major contributor to total BEM cell overpotential. Similar behavior has been reported by Ki et al. [28], who reported that potential losses associated to the pH split were dominant in a microbial electrolysis cell. On day 44, partial replacement of the catholyte from Electrolyte-A to Electrolyte-B resulted in a slight decrease in cell voltage; however, ionic losses increased marginally due to the lower conductivity and buffering capacity of the new electrolyte.

The elevated anode potentials observed throughout the experiment are consistent with the high overpotential associated with the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) under acidic conditions [12]. Although such

conditions may accelerate corrosion of metal-based anodes, no obvious operational evidence of degradation of the MMO anode was observed during the 83-day operational period, confirming the electrochemical robustness and long-term stability of the BEM stack under the applied conditions [29].

3.3. Influence of CO₂ injection strategy on CH₄ production

The BEM system operated with synthetic CO₂ gas, regularly injected into the catholyte to control the concentration of dissolved CO₂ within the desired range. Fig. 4 A shows the temporal evolution of volumetric CO₂ composition in the gas phase alongside the corresponding dissolved CO₂ in the liquid phase, over the entire experimental period. Fig. 4B displays the evolution of CH₄ production rate and its relative concentration in the gas mixture. A direct correlation was observed between the concentration of dissolved CO₂ in the catholyte, and its corresponding concentration in the produced cathodic biogas. Additionally, an inverse relationship was identified between dissolved CO₂ levels and all CH₄ performance indicators, including CH₄ production rate, gas purity and CE_{cat}. It should be noted that dissolved CO₂ concentration was manually regulated based on sensor readings, which introduced a degree of variability in the applied conditions. Therefore, the observed trends should be interpreted considering the limited precision in CO₂ control.

During the inoculation phase, when a current density of 6 A m⁻² was applied, a progressive increase in both CH₄ production and concentration was observed from day 4 onwards. Increasing the current to 12 A m⁻² while simultaneously reducing CO₂ feeding by lowering the upper limit of dissolved CO₂ concentration from 1.1 to 0.88 g L⁻¹, positively affected the average CH₄ purity, which rose from 62.7 \pm 5.8% to 68.0 \pm 4.3%, respectively (Table 3). However, no improvement in the CH₄ production rate was observed, which remained stable at 0.9 \pm 0.5 L-CH₄ L_{cathode}⁻¹ day⁻¹, suggesting that methane productivity was limited by microbial adaptation rather than electron or CO₂ availability during this phase.

From day 41 onward, the CH₄ production rate decreased to 0.2 \pm 0.1 L-CH₄ L_{cathode}⁻¹ day⁻¹ (78% decrease), which coincided with a rise in catholyte conductivity to 22 mS cm⁻¹ (Fig. 2A). This conductivity surpasses the upper limit of salinity tolerated by *Methanobacterium* (1.4 mol L⁻¹ that roughly corresponds with 18 mS cm⁻¹) [27], suggesting that high salinity contributed to the inhibition of methanogenesis [13]. To address this, 30% of Electrolyte-A was replaced with a less concentrated solution (Electrolyte-B) on day 44. This change led to an improvement in CH₄ production rate, increasing to 1.1 \pm 0.3 L-CH₄ L_{cathode}⁻¹ day⁻¹ (excluding the 7-day adaptation period following the exchange). This recovery can be attributed primarily to reduced ionic strength, as inferred from the catholyte conductivity.

Between days 64 and 76, the dissolved CO₂ concentration was regulated to remain between 0.66 and 0.22 g L⁻¹, resulting in a specific production rate of 1.1 \pm 0.4 L-CH₄ L_{cathode}⁻¹ day⁻¹ with an CH₄ purity of almost 86%. Further reducing the dissolved CO₂ to below 20% (days 76–83, light blue zone, Fig. 4) led to a further enhancement in CH₄ purity, reaching up to 88%, and an average CH₄ production rate of 1.1 \pm 0.3 L-CH₄ L_{cathode}⁻¹ day⁻¹. However, the manual regulation of CO₂ supply may have contributed to fluctuations in dissolved CO₂ levels, potentially affecting the stability of CH₄ production and CE_{cat}.

The relationship between dissolved CO₂ concentration and CH₄ purity can be partially explained by Henry's law, which governs the dissolution of CO₂ from the gas phase into the electrolyte. Higher CO₂ partial pressures increase its solubility, thereby enhancing the availability of dissolved inorganic carbon for electromethanogenic microorganisms. This can promote higher CH₄ production rates and improve CO₂ conversion efficiency.

However, excessively high CO₂ partial pressures also result in elevated CO₂ concentrations in the headspace, which can be detrimental to methane purity, as unconverted CO₂ directly dilutes the CH₄ fraction in the outlet gas. This highlights a trade-off between maximizing CO₂

Fig. 4. (A) Temporal trends of CO₂ and CH₄ dynamics in the system. Percentage of CO₂ in the gas phase (green plot) and dissolved CO₂ concentration (black plot) are represented over time. (B) Daily average CH₄ production rates (blue bars, expressed as L-CH₄ L⁻¹ cathode day⁻¹) and CH₄ percentage in the gas phase (orange plot) are represented over time. (C) Daily averages of CE_{cat} (green bars) and EE (dark red plot, expressed as kWh Nm⁻³-CH₄) are represented over time.

Table 3Average \pm standard deviation of specific CH₄ production rate and volumetric gas composition (CH₄ and CO₂) over the different operating conditions.

Time (days)	Current density (A m ⁻²)	Dissolved CO ₂ range		CH ₄ composition (%)	CO ₂ composition (%)	CH ₄ production rate (L-CH ₄ L _{cat} ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	CE _{cat} (%)	Energy consumption (kWh Nm ⁻³ -CH ₄)
		(%)	(g-CO ₂ L ⁻¹)					
0–14	6	100–50	1.1–0.55	40.5 \pm 4.7	31.1 \pm 3.2	0.2 \pm 0.3	28.5 \pm 36.5	33.5 \pm 21.9
15–21	12	100–50	1.1–0.55	62.7 \pm 5.8	22.9 \pm 4.8	0.9 \pm 0.5	55.7 \pm 33.2	38.7 \pm 14.6
21–44*	12	80–50	0.88–0.55	68.0 \pm 4.3	17.6 \pm 4.9	0.9 \pm 0.5	53.4 \pm 30.2	43.6 \pm 10.8
44	Catholyte exchange							
45** – 63	12	80–50	0.88–0.55	78.1 \pm 16.2	13.9 \pm 5.3	1.1 \pm 0.3	65.3 \pm 20.0	38.0 \pm 6.4
63	Anolyte exchange							
64–76	12	60–20	0.66–0.22	85.5 \pm 3.2	10.0 \pm 6.0	1.1 \pm 0.3	65.6 \pm 16.0	42.0 \pm 5.4
76–83	12	20–5	0.22–0.055	87.6 \pm 2.6	5.4 \pm 3.2	1.1 \pm 0.3	69.7 \pm 14.5	39.8 \pm 9.0

* Data up to day 41: although the period is indicated as days 21–44, the values correspond to data collected until day 41, when a stable CH₄ production rate was achieved.

** Data from day 52: although the period is indicated as days 45–63, the values correspond to data collected from day 52, when CH₄ production rate recovered after the catholyte exchange.

availability in the liquid phase and maintaining a high CH₄ purity in the gas phase. Therefore, optimizing CO₂ partial pressure is essential to balance substrate availability and quality of produced methane.

The CE_{cat} (Fig. 4C) showed a general increase during the first 40 days of BEM operation, followed by values ranging from 10% to 99%, indicating a very variable CE_{cat} associated with the adopted CO₂ feeding strategy. The maximum CH₄ production rate and CE_{cat} obtained (1.9 L-CH₄ L_{cathode}⁻¹ day⁻¹ and 99%, respectively) fall within the range of values reported in electromethanogenesis literature, for studies employing synthetic CO₂ [14,30].

Overall, these results demonstrate that regulating CO₂ injection is a critical operational parameter for simultaneously enhancing both CH₄ purity and production rate in BEM stacks. A semi-continuous injection strategy allowing to maintain a minimum dissolved CO₂ concentration in the catholyte (<0.22 g L⁻¹) through more frequent gas supply events would likely result in a more stable CH₄ production (and CE_{cat}) compared with intermittent feeding that maintains a higher dissolved CO₂ concentration (0.55 g L⁻¹) on the catholyte.

During the start-up phase, CE_{cat} for CH₄ production was the lowest observed throughout the operation (~20%, Fig. 4C). This low initial efficiency is typical in bioelectrochemical systems and is attributed to limited biomass and non-optimized microbial activity at the beginning of the experiment [23,31]. On day 48, due to catholyte exchange, E_{con} reached 243 kWh Nm⁻³-CH₄ (not shown in Fig. 4C). Subsequently, E_{con} stabilised on values between 27 and 47 kWh Nm⁻³-CH₄, indicating that the methanogenic community had established itself and adapted to Electrolyte-B, improving the overall E_{con} of the system.

During stable operation at 12 A m⁻², the average energy consumption was 40 \pm 7 kWh Nm⁻³, with a minimum value of 27 kWh Nm⁻³. These results are in reasonable agreement with literature data for electromethanogenesis. For instance, energy consumption for CH₄ production ranges from 26 to 35 Wh L-CH₄⁻¹ for pilot scale thermochemical methanation, where hydrogen is supplied by electrolysis and subsequently converted to CH₄ via the Sabatier process, and 19 Wh L⁻¹-CH₄ for biochemical methanation [2]. Specifically for BEM, minimum energy consumption values of approximately 20 kWh Nm⁻³ have been achieved [32,33]. Although our average value was slightly higher, the minimum measured value fell within the lower range reported for BEM systems.

3.4. Net ion crossover

Ion crossover rates of selected anions and cations can be primarily attributed to the net migration of ions across the CEM, driven by the

electric field and concentration gradients of the different ionic species, within the anode and cathode compartments of the BEM stack. The resulting ion fluxes are reported in Fig. 5 for both compartments cross the 83-day operation, defined in Table 2.

When using 0.1 M PPMS as anolyte (from day 0 to day 63), Cl⁻ concentration in the cathode compartment showed a decreasing trend, attributed to its crossing toward the anodic compartment (Fig. 5A). Although exchanging the PPMS anolyte to Electrolyte-B on day 64 helped mitigate Cl⁻ transport, it did not completely prevent it (Table 4, top). After the exchange, the Cl⁻ concentration in the anolyte increased to 17.6 mM (Fig. 5A), reflecting the Cl⁻ content of Electrolyte-B used for the substitution (18.5 mM). In the subsequent days, the anolyte Cl⁻ concentration decreased to 9.5 mM. While this decline could suggest Cl⁻ crossover from the anode to the cathode, the simultaneous decrease in Cl⁻ in the cathode as indicated by a negative *iCl* (Table 4, top) indicates continued net transport from cathode to anode. This behavior is more plausibly explained by anodic consumption of chloride via oxidation to chlorine gas (Cl₂). Although Cl₂ was not analytically detected, its formation could not be excluded, as suggested by qualitative olfactory observations consistent with chlorine presence. This is consistent with the anode BEM potential (2 V vs Ag/AgCl at 12 A m⁻²), which exceeds the standard oxidation potential of chloride (1.36 V vs SHE) [34], enabling Cl₂ formation at the IrO₂ MMO anode. The generation of Cl₂ can have detrimental effects on the system, including corrosion of metallic components and equipment, degradation of polymeric seals, tubing, and membranes, interference with analytical sensors, and, in biological systems, inhibition of microbial activity [25]. Although these detrimental effects were not observed during the experiment, Cl₂ generation should be carefully monitored or prevented. Reducing chloride concentration in the initial anolyte formulation represents a straightforward mitigation strategy. Notably, Lang et al. [16] reported that eliminating chloride ions from the system has no detrimental effect on the biocatalyst and effectively avoids Cl₂ formation.

Among the anions, PO₄³⁻ showed the most prominent contribution to charge transport, particularly during inoculation (days 0–14) and until anolyte exchange (day 63). This is attributed to the use of PPMS 0.1 M as the anolyte and its trivalent charge, resulting in a high concentration gradient driving a net flux of PO₄³⁻ ions from the anode to the cathode. Whereas SO₄²⁻ remained at low concentrations (<0.5 mM, Fig. 5B) throughout the experiment, showing minimal transport overall (on the order of 10⁻⁵ to 10⁻⁴ C s⁻¹ m⁻²). Following the anolyte exchange, PO₄³⁻ transport pattern reversed, and the anode *iSO*₄²⁻ incremented to almost 1.3 · 10⁻² C s⁻¹ m⁻².

Fig. 5. Temporal evolution of ion concentrations in the anolyte during the experiment. The panels show the concentrations of Cl^- (A), SO_4^{2-} (B), PO_4^{3-} (C), Na^+ (D), K^+ (E), Ca^{2+} (F), and Mg^{2+} (G). Dashed purple vertical lines indicate the catholyte exchange (day 44) and the anolyte exchange (day 63).

Table 4

Anions (top) and cations (bottom) contribution to the total charge transport in the BEM in $C s^{-1} m^{-2}$ membrane. Positive values indicate flux that enters the electrochemical chamber (cathode or anode), whereas negative values represent a flux that exits the chamber.

Time (days)	iCl^- Cathode	iCl^- Anode	iSO_4^{2-} Cathode	iSO_4^{2-} Anode	iPO_4^{3-} Cathode	iPO_4^{3-} Anode		
0-14	$-4.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$-8.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$8.4 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-9.3 \cdot 10^{-1}$		
15-21	$-2.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-8.3 \cdot 10^{-2}$		
21-44	$-1.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-2.5 \cdot 10^{-1}$		
44	Catholyte exchange							
45-63	$-3.8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-2}$		
63	Anolyte exchange							
64-76	$-9.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-5.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-	$6.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-1.0 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$		
76-83	$-1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-2.6 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-	$6.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-8.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$		
Time (days)	iNa^+ Cathode	iNa^+ Anode	iK^+ Cathode	iK^+ Anode	iCa^{2+} Cathode	iCa^{2+} Anode	iMg^{2+} Cathode	iMg^{2+} Anode
0-14	$3.2 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-3.6 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$3.4 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-1.5 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$
15-21	$9.8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-9.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-5.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
21-44	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-6.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-6.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-	-	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
44	Catholyte exchange							
45-63	$3.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-2.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-5.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
63	Anolyte exchange							
64-76	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-3.2 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-4.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-5.4 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-2.4 \cdot 10^{-2}$
76-83	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-5.8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-7.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$-4.6 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-	$-2.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-

For the cations, Na^+ and K^+ (Fig. 5D and E, respectively) were the predominant charge carriers, with transport from the anode to the cathode (Table 4, bottom). Divalent cations, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , (Fig. 5F and G, respectively) contributed substantially less and with greater variability, often showing low or inconsistent fluxes and concentrations

through the experiment.

Interestingly, replacing the catholyte (day 44) helped to reduce the accumulation of PO_4^{3-} , Na^+ and K^+ in the cathode chamber, while replacing the anolyte (day 63), reversed the iK^+ trend. The transport of cations like Na^+ and K^+ through the CEM was expected, driven by the

Fig. 6. Taxonomic composition of microbial communities in the reactor throughout the experimental period, divided into two operational phases. (A) Relative abundance of bacterial genera (%). (B) Differential taxonomic composition at the genus level.

electrical field. However, despite the CEM design to repel anions, our results indicated that anions like Cl⁻ and PO₄³⁻ also crossed the membrane, most likely by diffusion, driven by the initial concentration gradients between the two electrolytes ([Cl⁻]_{anode} ≈ 0 vs [Cl⁻]_{cathode} ≈ 20 mM, Fig. 5A and ([PO₄³⁻]_{anode} > 600 mM vs [PO₄³⁻]_{cathode} ≈ 60 mM, Fig. 5C). Because the concentration of PO₄³⁻ was substantially higher than those of Cl⁻, its contribution to charge transport across the membrane was correspondingly (greater by approximately one order of magnitude).

Ion crossover in the CEM indicated that most of the ionic charge was transported by species other than H⁺, increasing the concentration gradient and ionic resistance. Changing the anolyte and catholyte affected both ion distribution and transport, showing that operational adjustments can improve performance. Diffusion, even for multivalent ions, also played a significant role in the BEM system operating under strong ionic gradients. These findings provide guidance for optimizing BEM systems while minimizing negative effects from ion crossover.

3.5. Microbial community structure in the BEM catholyte

During Phase 1, the suspended biomass in the BEM catholyte was dominated by the genera *Azonexus* (7.8–26.3%), *Acetobacterium* (14.4–38.0%), *Alistipes* (6.5–11.3%), *Gudongella* (8.3–18.9%), *Pseudomonas* (6.6–10.6%) and *Tepidimonas* (2.6–9.3%), as shown in Fig. 6A. In Phase 2, the microbial community experienced a marked readjustment, especially on day 45, likely as a combined effect of the reinoculation performed at the end of Phase 1 and the partial replacement (30%) of Electrolyte-A on day 44 (Table 2). However, from day 45 onwards, a progressive increase in the relative abundance of *Azonexus* (20.5–43.3%), *Alistipes* (2.0–12.9%), *Gudongella* (0–7.5%) and *Tepidimonas* (3.1–5.7%) was observed, consolidating them as stable members of the community towards the end of the experiment. Although our microbial profiling targeted the bulk catholyte rather than the electrode-attached biofilm, the dominant taxa detected in the catholyte can reflect key members of the cathodic consortium at the system level, based on Authors experience.

Among the dominant genera identified in our system, *Azonexus* was particularly abundant, especially during Phase 2, establishing itself as a stable member of the community. Previous studies have shown that *Azonexus* is enriched on biocathodes under applied potentials and decreases in abundance when the external potential is suspended [7]. The recurrent enrichment observed here is therefore consistent with a putative role of this genus in cathodic electron fluxes. Given its reported capacity for extracellular electron transfer, *Azonexus* may contribute either by mediating electron exchange with other community members or by directly participating in cathode-associated electron uptake. In both cases, its activity could indirectly favour conditions that support downstream hydrogenotrophic and acetoclastic methanogenesis. Nevertheless, confirming its spatial enrichment at the electrode surface will require direct biofilm-focused analyses.

Methane production in the BEM stack likely proceeded via a combination of direct electromethanogenesis and indirect pathways involving acetate as a metabolic intermediate. The absence of detectable acetate throughout the experiment (below the detection limit, <0.1 mg L⁻¹) is consistent with this interpretation. *Acetobacterium* was detected in both operational phases but was more abundant during Phase 1. This period coincided with an increase in catholyte pH and conductivity (Fig. 2) and, towards the end of the phase, with a decline in both CH₄ production rate and CE_{cat} (Fig. 4B and C). Similar conditions were previously reported to favour the growth of *Acetobacterium* spp. on cathode surfaces, promoting acetate formation under alkaline conditions and limited H⁺ availability, ultimately reducing the energy efficiency of the BEM system [32].

In the present study, the high abundance of *Acetobacterium* during Phase 1 may have resulted in elevated acetate production; however, neither acetate nor other VFAs were detected. The combination of potential acetate overproduction and high salinity may nevertheless have

constrained methanogenic activity. Notably, no competitive carbon sinks were detected throughout the experiment, indicating that the supplied carbon was ultimately converted to methane via hydrogenotrophic and/or acetoclastic pathways.

In contrast, during Phase 2, when cathodic conditions were more stable, *Acetobacterium* remained at a lower relative abundance. This suggests a more balanced role within the community, acting as a primary acetate producer whose activity was effectively coupled to acetoclastic methanogenesis [33]. Under these conditions, higher methane production rates and purities were achieved (up to 86% on day 76), supporting the hypothesis that *Acetobacterium* contributes positively to system performance when its acetogenic activity remains in equilibrium with downstream methanogenic processes and does not lead to acetate accumulation.

Beta diversity analysis showed a significant effect of the operating regime on the community structure (Supplementary Information, PERMANOVA, R = 0.5, p < 0.05; Fig. S3), indicating that operational changes can substantially reorganize the microbial ecosystem once established. At the genus level, 20 taxa exhibited significantly different abundances between phases (adjusted FDR < 0.05; Fig. 6B), suggesting selective responses to operational conditions that likely reflect functional adaptations relevant to system performance.

Interestingly, the microbial dynamics observed in this study differ from those reported by Zhang et al. [35], where excess H₂ favoured the co-enrichment of *Methanobacterium* and *Acetoanaerobium*, establishing a thermodynamically favourable current-acetate-hydrogen cycle. In contrast, during the first 14 days of our experiment, a current density of 6 A m⁻² was applied and no H₂ accumulation was detected, indicating efficient consumption of reducing equivalents via electromethanogenesis. After increasing the current density to 12 A m⁻² on day 14, no excess H₂ was observed, yet *Acetoanaerobium* became differentially abundant during Phase 2, coinciding with improved system stability and enhanced methane production.

These results suggest that, in the BEM stack, the abundance of *Acetoanaerobium* is not driven by excess electrochemically generated H₂. Instead, it likely reflects a more efficient functional coupling between the production of intermediates (acetate and hydrogen) and their consumption by methanogens, thereby promoting overall system stability. Previous studies have shown that *Acetoanaerobium* can use electrons from external donors to reduce CO₂ to acetate, modulating methanogenic community dynamics and enhancing microbial resilience [36]. In the present system, the cathode may play an analogous role by supplying reducing equivalents, enabling efficient acetate generation and ultimately optimising CO₂ conversion to CH₄.

3.6. Functional interpretation and correlations with BEM system performance

A limitation of our community analysis is that methanogenic archaea were not detected in the 16S rRNA amplicon dataset, despite clear evidence of active methanogenesis based on methane production. This is most likely attributable to primer-related bias inherent to the Oxford Nanopore SQK-16S114.24 (V14) workflow (Nanopore store: 16S Barcoding Kit 24 V14). The kit relies on commercially provided “universal” primers that are primarily designed for genus-level bacterial identification and target regions that are not fully conserved across all taxa. Consequently, amplification is not guaranteed for all organisms, and archaeal lineages may be under-represented in mixed communities. This interpretation is consistent with previous Nanopore-based studies showing strong primer-dependence, in which archaeal taxa were not recovered using universal/bacterial primers but were successfully detected when archaeal-targeted primers were employed [37].

To overcome the incomplete detection of methanogens in our amplicon data, we therefore quantified the functional marker genes *mcrA* and *hdrA* by qPCR. These genes are specific to the terminal steps of hydrogenotrophic and acetoclastic methanogenesis and provide a more

reliable estimate of methanogenic abundance and activity than 16S-based surveys when primer mismatches compromise archaeal amplification. Thus, while the 16S Nanopore dataset in this study primarily reflects the bacterial fraction of the biocathode community, the *mcrA* and *hdrA* qPCR data allow us to still characterize and quantify the methanogenic archaea that drive CH₄ conversion.

Spearman correlation analysis (Fig. 7) revealed distinct relationships between dominant bacterial genera, operational parameters (including catholyte conductivity), methane production rate, and methanogenic gene abundance. During Phase 1, genera such as *Acetobacterium*, *Yersinia*, *Entomomonas*, *Pinisolibacter*, *Andresenia* and *Enterobacter* showed significant negative correlations with *mcrA* and *hdrA* copy numbers. In several cases, these taxa also exhibited positive, although not always significant, correlations with conductivity. This pattern is consistent with the elevated salinity and alkaline pH observed during Phase 1, conditions that may have constrained methanogenic activity while favouring the proliferation of taxa less directly associated with methane production.

In contrast, Phase 2 was characterized by the consolidation of a more specialized and functionally integrated community. Genera such as *Xanthobacter*, *Anaerospromusa* and *Comamonas* exhibited positive correlations with *mcrA*, *hdrA* and methane production rate, although not all relationships reached statistical significance. *Azonexus*, present throughout both phases, also showed a positive correlation with methane production, reinforcing its proposed role as a stable and functionally relevant member of the consortium.

Notably, strong positive correlations were observed between *Lentimicrobium*, *Oryzisolibacter* and *Rhodopseudomonas* with both methanogenic gene abundance and methane production. These associations suggest close metabolic interactions with methanogenic archaea. This interpretation aligns with previous studies on anaerobic digestion under high butyrate loading, where *Lentimicrobium* was identified as a key functional taxon alongside *Methanosarcina* and *Syntrophomonas*,

contributing to process stability and methane production efficiency [38]. Although butyrate was not externally supplied in the present BEM system, the increased abundance of *Lentimicrobium* during Phase 2 and its positive correlations with methanogenic activity suggest a comparable functional role. Specifically, it may act as a support bacterium producing intermediates such as H₂ and acetate from available substrates at the cathode, thereby facilitating stable CH₄ conversion and preventing the accumulation of inhibitory metabolites for methanogenesis.

The presence of *Comamonas* in the catholyte further suggests potential involvement in liquid-phase mediated electron transfer or redox compound recycling, contributing to the electrochemical balance of the BEM system. Previous studies in denitrifying microbial fuel cells have identified *Comamonas* as an electroactive genus capable of extracellular electron transfer and stable biofilm formation under anaerobic conditions [39]. Moreover, *Comamonas testosteroni* I2 has been shown to adapt its electron transfer mechanisms according to electrochemical conditions, utilizing both surface-attached redox species and soluble mediators across different potentials [40]. In the context of this study, the presence of *Comamonas* in the bulk suggests that this genus may contribute to system-level electron availability, which could indirectly support biofilm stability and downstream acetogenic and methanogenic processes. This points to a potential electroactive role beyond its classical functions in organic matter degradation or denitrification, without implying direct involvement within the electrode-attached biofilm.

3.7. Integrated system behavior and scalability of BEM systems

The results obtained in this study demonstrate that the optimal performances of BEM systems emerge from the strong coupling between electrochemical operation, chemical conditions and microbial dynamics, and therefore cannot be fully understood by considering these aspects in isolation. Electrochemical parameters such as current density

Fig. 7. Spearman correlation heatmap showing relationships between dominant genera, CH₄ production rate, biocathode conductivity, and copy numbers of *mcrA* and *hdrA* genes.

and cell voltage determine the rate of electron supply, but their effective utilization is governed by chemical constraints, including electrolyte conductivity, ion transport across membranes, dissolved CO₂ availability and target quality of the desired product. Increasing the current density from 6 to 12 A m⁻² did not result in hydrogen accumulation, indicating efficient biological consumption of reducing equivalents; however, the concurrent increase in overpotentials and internal resistance highlights the growing importance of ionic transport limitations at higher loads.

These physicochemical conditions directly influenced microbial activity and community structure. Elevated catholyte conductivity, driven by ionic crossover, was associated with decreased methane production rates and lower Coulombic efficiencies, suggesting that salinity and electrolyte imbalance can inhibit methanogenic performance. In contrast, electrolyte replacement restored favourable conditions, leading to recovery of microbial activity and stabilization of CH₄ production. This demonstrates that electrolyte composition and ion transport regulate system performance not only through electrochemical losses but also via their impact on microbial viability and metabolic activity.

Similarly, dissolved CO₂ concentration acted as a key linking parameter between system domains. Lower dissolved CO₂ levels improved methane purity and Coulombic efficiency, indicating a more effective coupling between electron supply and carbon conversion pathways. This suggests that CO₂ availability controls both gas-phase composition and microbial metabolism, reinforcing its role as a critical operational variable.

At microbial level, the transition toward a more stable and functionally coordinated community further supports this integrated interpretation. The observed correlations between bacterial populations, methanogenic functional genes (*mcrA* and *hdrA*), and methane production indicate that microbial community dynamics are shaped by the electrochemical and chemical environment, leading to the establishment of a cooperative metabolic network that enhances system efficiency.

From a practical perspective, these findings have direct implications for the scale-up and application of BEM systems. The results highlight that ionic crossover, electrolyte management, and CO₂ delivery become dominant factors at stack level, where their effects are amplified compared to single-cell systems. The mitigation strategies proposed in this study, including periodic electrolyte replacement and operation under controlled conductivity conditions, provide feasible approaches to maintain long-term stability. Moreover, the use of galvanostatic control enables matching electron supply with biological demand, which is particularly relevant for coupling BEM systems with intermittent renewable energy sources in power-to-gas applications [5]. Despite these promising results, several challenges remain for large-scale deployment. These include the need to reduce internal resistances associated with membrane transport, prevent undesired side reactions such as chlorine evolution under certain electrolyte compositions, and further optimize electrode materials to sustain higher current densities. Additionally, automation of CO₂ dosing and electrolyte management will be essential to ensure stable long-term operation under industrial conditions.

4. Conclusions

In this study, a lab-scale BEM stack was optimized in three correlated aspects. First, electrolytes composition was investigated. Operating with Electrolyte-A as catholyte, which provided high conductivity, led to salt accumulation and microbial inhibition due to cations crossover through the CEM. To mitigate this effect, substitution with Electrolyte-B was implemented. This medium, with lower conductivity and composition closer to real wastewater effluents, effectively reduced salinity build-up, without compromising the electrochemical efficiency of the BEM. Electrochemical characterization indicated that overpotentials linked to the pH gradient between the electrolytes dominated to the overall

overpotential. It helped guided the optimization of electrolyte formulation toward a balance between sufficient conductivity for the BEM system and microbial biocompatibility.

Second, applied current density, which dictates the availability of reducing equivalents for electromethanogenesis. Operating initially at 6 A m⁻² allowed full consumption of electrons without H₂ accumulation, while increasing the current to 12 A m⁻² after 14 days optimized CH₄ production, demonstrating that fine-tuning electron flow to match the CO₂ supply is critical. This highlights that galvanostatic control enables effective scaling by preventing electron over-supply and maintaining high conversion efficiency.

Finally, the CO₂ injection strategy proved essential for achieving efficient methanogenesis and high CH₄ purity. The best results (0.96 ± 0.33 L-CH₄ L⁻¹ cathode d⁻¹ with a CH₄ purity close to 90%) were obtained under low dissolved CO₂ conditions. These findings should be interpreted considering the limitations associated with the manual regulation of dissolved CO₂ concentration, which may have introduced variability in substrate availability throughout the experiments. At microbiological level, community profiling combined with functional gene quantification demonstrated that stable and efficient CH₄ conversion depends on a balance between electroactive, homoacetogenic and methanogenic populations. Although methanogenic archaea were not detected in the 16S rRNA Nanopore dataset, qPCR of *mcrA* and *hdrA* confirmed active hydrogenotrophic and acetoclastic methanogenesis, underscoring the need for functional markers when primer bias limits archaeal detection.

Altogether, these findings demonstrate that BEM stacks can achieve stable and efficient methane production under conditions relevant to scale-up, provided that electrolyte composition, ion transport and CO₂ delivery are carefully controlled. These findings contribute to bridging the gap between laboratory-scale research and industrial application of bioelectrochemical technologies for renewable methane production.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Daniele Molognoni: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sebastià Puig:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Eduard Borràs:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Marina Martín-Sandoval:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Data curation. **Amanda Gómez-Rodríguez:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Radu Ghemis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources. **Pablo Sánchez-Cueto:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Simone Colantoni:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maria Vega-Paredes:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation.

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Declarations

During the preparation of this work the authors used COPILOT in order to improve readability of the text. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcou.2026.103460](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2026.103460). The dataset corresponding to this paper has been published in Zenodo repository, with DOI [10.5281/zenodo.16994844](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16994844).

Data availability

I have shared the link to my data (Zenodo) at the Attach Files step.

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CE_{cat}: Coulombic efficiency
CEM: Cation exchange membrane
GC: Gas chromatograph
HER: Hydrogen evolution reaction
LSV: Linear Sweep Voltammetry
OD₆₀₀: Optical density at $\lambda = 600$ nm
OER: Oxygen evolution reaction
SHE: Standard hydrogen electrode
VFA: Volatile Fatty Acids

Glossary

BEM: Bioelectrochemical methanation